

Biosorption of cyanide using *Bacillus cereus* from Salt Pan, Tuticorin, Tamilnadu – Isotherm and kinetic studies

S. Padmavathy^a, N. K. Asha Devi^a and D. S. Bhuvaneshwari^{*b}

^aDepartment of Zoology and Microbiology, Thiagarajar College, Madurai-625 009, Tamilnadu, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Thiagarajar College, Madurai-625 009, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : bukanch@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : In the present study, with the aim of isolating cyanide degrading organisms, four different Gram-positive, aerobic, endospore-forming bacteria (S1 to S4) having the ability to degrade cyanide were isolated by enrichment technique from salt pan region. They were identified as *Bacillus* sp. and were subjected to cyanide biodegradation assay. Based on the results obtained in cyanide and ammonia estimation, the strain S3 *Bacillus cereus* was found to show maximum biodegradation ability. The potential isolate S3 was confirmed as *Bacillus cereus* and submitted in NCBI with the accession number FJ267613. The selected isolate S3 was employed for biodegradation assay in minimal medium which showed that the degradation was higher, in the medium supplemented with glucose. Thereafter optimization studies at different pH, temperature, inoculum concentration, glucose concentration were done which showed that the alkaliphilic *Bacillus cereus* showed their degradation potential elevated in minimal medium at pH 8, 35 °C, 2% inoculum concentration and at 3% glucose concentration. The degradation kinetics was found to be best represented by pseudo-second order kinetic model. The Tempkin isotherm was the best fit isotherm for the degradation of cyanide under experimental conditions used in this study ($R^2 = 0.996$). Henceforth it can be concluded from the present investigation that there is a high potentiality for alkaliphilic isolate to degrade cyanide in effluent streams very effectively.

Keywords : Biosorption, cyanide, nitrile compounds, haloalkalophiles, *Bacillus cereus*, cyanotrophic bacteria.

Introduction

Many lethal compounds are entering into the environment, due to industrialization and modernization. Cyanide is one among them playing an imperative role in polluting the surrounding environment. Cyanide compounds, both organic and inorganic are found widely distributed on our planet. Indeed they have been postulated to have played a key role in the prebiotic chemistry that led to the evolution of biological macromolecules and primitive life¹.

Cyanide is a carbon nitrogen radical, which may be found in a wide variety of life forms and their large scale presence in the environment is attributed to the manufactured sources which are used extensively in industries^{2,3}. Cyanide is commonly found in wastewaters from various applications and industries including metal cleaning, electroplating, metal processing, automobile parts manufacture, steel tempering, mining, nuclear processing, pho-

tography, pharmaceuticals, coal coking, ore leaching, plastics, pesticides, fumigants, fire retardants etc.⁴⁻⁷. However, in recent years there is a growing concern on the potential toxicity due to huge amount of cyanide containing wastes generated through anthropogenic activity.

Over one million tons of cyanide (about 80% of the annual product of cyanide compounds) is used in the chemical industries for the production of organic chemicals such as nylon and acrylics, in electroplating, metal processing and photographic applications⁸⁻¹⁰. Cyanide has been the preferred lixiviant worldwide since 1887 in extracting gold and other metals such as silver, copper and zinc from ores. Each year, over a billion tons of gold ore are treated using this process¹¹⁻¹³, which means a significant demand for cyanide by these industries. According to some estimates up to 90% of gold is produced using cyanide¹⁴.

Therefore, control and remediation of cyanide-con-

taminated water is desired because of the potential hazards associated with cyanide. There are several conventional methods used in treating effluents containing cyanide before discharging it into the environment. The most common ones are the alkaline chlorination, sulfur oxide/air process and hydrogen peroxide process². Even though these methods of treatment can be used in detoxifying free cyanide bearing waste, they pose significant drawbacks such as infirmity to treat cyanide that is complexed with metals, high costs of reagents and equipments, the generation of unfavorable by-product such as chlorinated compounds. Thus, with rapid growth in many applications that utilize cyanide, it is necessary to use bioremediation as the most promising platform to prevent contamination of soils and wastewater.

Biosorption is a proven technology for the removal of metal ions from synthetic and real industrial effluents. The high cost of activated carbon has motivated scientists into the search for new low cost adsorption means. Many attempts to develop biological processes for the detoxification of cyanide have been concentrated on cyanide-degrading fungi and several studies have been established on the use of bacterial strains such as *Klebsiella*, *Pseudomonas*, *Acinetobacter*, *Bacillus*, *Burkholderia* and *Alcaligenes*¹⁵. Microorganisms are able to convert cyanide into other less toxic products like ammonia, formic acid and formamide depending upon the enzyme system they possess^{16,17}.

Alkaliphiles are the organisms thriving in harsh alkaline conditions. Although alkaliphiles are being employed for environmental cleanup¹⁸, the literature regarding the study of alkaliphiles vis-à-vis aromatic amines or cyanide degradation is less reported as compared to the other degradation studies. The organisms living in such dual extreme environment possess special adaptation strategies that make them interesting not only for fundamental research but also towards the exploration of its applications particularly in the production of commercial compounds and degradation of toxic compounds. As a result of adaptation to extreme environments, extremophiles have evolved unique properties with biotechnological and commercial significance¹⁹.

Keeping the above facts in view, the present work was attempted to study the potentiality of *Bacillus cereus*

from the salt pan by acclimatizing the microorganisms to the commercial cyanide compounds. The effect of factors such as pH, temperature, inoculum concentration, and glucose concentration on cyanide degradation was investigated. Experimental equilibrium data were fitted to the Langmuir, Freundlich, Tempkin isotherm equations to determine the best-fit isotherm model. The degradation capacity of cyanide by haloalkaliphilic *Bacillus cereus* was evaluated using zero order, pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order rate kinetic models.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents : Sodium cyanide was obtained from SD Fine Chemicals Ltd., India. The medium components were procured from Himedia Ltd., Mumbai, India, and molecular biology grade chemicals from Bangalore Genei Pvt. Ltd., India. Glasswares were purchased from Borosil Glass Pvt. Ltd., India.

Area of study : The samples were collected from four different salt pan areas of Tuticorin. The collected samples were used as a source for isolating haloalkaliphilic *Bacillus* species.

Sample collection : The samples were collected aseptically in a sterilized screw cap bottles. The accessories used for collection were steam sterilized for 15 min at 121 °C. The collected samples were stored at refrigerated condition for further isolation procedure.

Enrichment and isolation of cyanide degrading bacteria : The enrichment of four samples collected from different salt pan regions, were done by acclimatizing in cyanide containing minimal medium. The native isolate was exposed to different concentrations of sodium cyanide by repeated sub culturing in fresh medium. The *Bacillus* species isolates were selected based on colony morphology from four different samples by spread plate method. They were maintained in enrichment medium supplemented with sodium cyanide for further analysis.

Identification of the isolate : The cyanide degrading microbial isolates were identified by colonial, morphological and biochemical characteristics as per the guidelines of Bergey's manual of Bacteriology^{20,21}.

Collection of cyanide effluent : Cyanide containing waste sample was collected from gold processing industry in Trichy. The presence of cyanide in the sample was

analysed by field testing method²².

Preparation of standard graph for cyanide : The standard graph for cyanide was performed according to Phenolphthalein copper method. The unknown concentration of the cyanide in the effluent sample was determined by comparing with the standard graph for cyanide.

Cyanide biodegradation assay : The effluent sample was subjected to filter sterilization in 0.2 μ membrane filter, to remove the residential isolates in them. 50 ml of enrichment media supplemented with 1 ml of cyanide containing sample were used for the degradation studies. 1 ml of culture suspension of four different isolates was inoculated in four separate conical flasks, incubated at 37 °C. At regular intervals (24, 48, 72 and 96 h) samples were analyzed to estimate the amount of cyanide by Phenolphthalein copper method.

Preparation of standard graph for ammonia : Nessler's method was adopted for ammonia estimation. Ammonia that is released as a product of cyanide degradation was analyzed by Nessler's method. After incubation for 72 and 96 h, the cyanide degraded samples were subjected for ammonia estimation. The unknown concentration of ammonia in the sample was determined by comparing with the standard graph for ammonia.

16S rDNA sequencing : The efficient isolate was identified by sequencing the partial sequences of their 16S rRNA gene. The isolation of DNA was done according to Janardhanan and Vincent²³. The partial 16S rRNA was amplified according to Rochelle *et al.*²⁴. Partial DNA obtained from PCR was sent to Chromus Biotech, Chennai, for sequencing purpose. The sequences of the partial 16S rRNA were compared with the 16S rRNA sequence available in the public nucleotide databases at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) by using its World Wide Web site (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>), and the BLAST (basic local alignment search tool) algorithm.

Isotherm models : Degradation equilibrium isotherms were studied using haloalkaliphilic *Bacillus* species with the cyanide concentration of 940 ppm/ml (cyanide/minimal medium). Initial concentration was fixed as 940 ppm/ml (cyanide/minimal medium) at neutral pH. In all sets of experiments, the plugged conical flasks were shaken with a speed of 120 rpm at different time intervals. Then, the

solution was separated from the mixture and analyzed for cyanide concentration. The degradation capacity was obtained by using a mass equilibrium equation as follows :

$$q = (C_0 - C_e)V/m \quad (1)$$

where C_0 and C_e being the initial cyanide concentration (ppm/ml) and equilibrium concentration, respectively, V is the experimental volume of cyanide solution expressed in milliliters, and m is the biomass expressed in milligrams. The effect of pH on the rate of degradation was investigated using cyanide concentration of 940 ppm/ml (cyanide/minimal medium) for constant bacillus dosages (1%). The adsorbent-adsorbate mixture was shaken at room temperature using agitation speed (120 rpm) for different time intervals. Then, the concentration of cyanide in solution was determined.

Biodegradation kinetics : The kinetic experiments were performed using different microorganisms for initial cyanide concentrations of 940 ppm. The experimental kinetic data were fitted by pseudo-second order models. The linearized forms of the pseudo-first order model and pseudo-second order^{1,2} are shown below in eqs. (1) and (2), respectively :

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \quad (1)$$

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + t/q_e \quad (2)$$

where, q_e is the amount of cyanide sample degradation at equilibrium per mass unit of sorbent (mg/ml), q_t is the amount of cyanide degradation at time t per mass unit of sorbent (mg/ml), k_1 the pseudo-first order rate constant (in h) and k_2 is the pseudo-second order rate constant (g/mg/h).

Optimization studies : Among the four *Bacillus* species, one isolate (S3) was selected for optimization studies. Initially biodegradation studies were done in enrichment medium containing carbon source (1% glucose). The optimization studies were employed for selected potential *Bacillus cereus* at different pH (5–9), temperature (25–45 °C), inoculum concentration (1–5%) and glucose concentration (1–5%). The fermentation was carried out up to 96 h of incubation. After incubation, cyanide and ammonia estimation were done as per the procedure referred before.

Results and discussion

The collected samples were used as a source for iso-

lating cyanide utilizing organisms. Totally four *Bacillus* species isolates were obtained based on colony morphology by enrichment technique using sodium cyanide. Based on the cultural, microscopical and biochemical evidences, the 4 isolates were tentatively identified as *Bacillus cereus* by their Lecithinase activity on *Bacillus cereus* agar medium and named as S1-S4. The organisms were further confirmed by the following biochemical test results which showed negative result for indole, methyl red and positive result for voges proskauer, citrate utilization, motility, starch hydrolysis, casein hydrolysis, gelatine hydrolysis, nitrate reduction, egg yolk lecithinase and catalase tests.

The concentration of cyanide in the gold processing waste sample was estimated by Phenolphthalein copper method and found to be 940 ppm/ml (cyanide/effluent sample). Four isolates of *Bacillus cereus* were subjected to cyanide biodegradation assay. The residual amount of cyanide in the sample was estimated from 24 to 96 h of incubation by plotting with the standard graph for cyanide. From the results, it was revealed that strain S3 showed maximum degradation of about 67.02% was obtained when compared to other three strains (Table 1). Despite the well-known toxicity of cyanide to living organisms²⁵, biological treatments are feasible alternatives

to physical and chemical methods²⁶, because a wide range of organisms are known to utilize such toxic chemicals as sources of energy or nutrition²⁷. Some organisms use cyanide as a nitrogen source and some others as both nitrogen and carbon source^{28,29}.

Ammonia, a by-product of cyanide released during cyanide degradation was also estimated by comparing with the standard graph for ammonia. The amount of ammonia was found to be released maximum at 72 h (32 µg/ml) and at 96 h of incubation (43 µg/ml) (Table 2). Based on the results obtained for cyanide and ammonia estimation strain S3 has more ability in metabolizing cyanide when compared to other *Bacillus cereus* isolates. Similar biodegradation studies were done in enrichment medium containing carbon source (1% glucose). Cyanide degradation by *Bacillus cereus* was observed maximum 98.79% in the presence of 1% dextrose (Tables 3 and 4). The amount of ammonia was found to be released maximum at 96 h of incubation (43 µg/ml). The effect of contact time for the biosorption of cyanide by *Bacillus cereus* at 940 ppm is shown in Fig. 1. The maximum removal of 79% was attained at 96 h.

The effect of varying doses of *Bacillus cereus* was investigated using different percentage of inoculums. Table 5 shows an increase in percentage in biosorption of cya-

Table 1. Estimation of degraded cyanide by different isolated strains

Organism	Hrs	OD values	Cyanide concentration (ppm/ml)	Degraded cyanide (ppm/ml)	Percentage of degradation	Biomass (mg/ml)
S1	24	0.531	780	160	17.02	1.96
	48	0.494	720	220	23.40	2.54
	72	0.417	590	350	37.23	6.03
	96	0.364	530	410	43.61	6.96
S2	24	0.621	910	30	3.19	0.32
	48	0.587	850	90	9.57	0.94
	72	0.539	780	160	17.02	1.95
	96	0.492	710	230	24.46	2.68
S3	24	0.552	800	140	14.89	1.74
	48	0.431	620	320	34.04	5.89
	72	0.327	470	470	50.00	9.98
	96	0.219	310	630	67.02	18.90
S4	24	0.619	900	40	4.25	0.38
	48	0.591	860	80	8.51	0.86
	72	0.554	800	140	14.89	1.74
	96	0.497	720	240	25.53	2.98

Table 2. Estimation of ammonia in enrichment media after 72 and 96 h

Organism	72 h of incubation			96 h of incubation		
	OD values	Concentration of ammonia (µg/ml)	Biomass (mg/ml)	OD values	Concentration of ammonia (µg/ml)	Biomass (mg/ml)
S1	0.236	24.19	6.03	0.295	28.34	6.96
S2	0.113	11.063	1.95	0.182	15.89	2.68
S3	0.352	32.50	9.98	0.443	43.56	18.90
S4	0.210	9.678	1.74	0.181	16.59	2.98

Table 3. Estimation of cyanide in enrichment media supplemented with 1% glucose for *Bacillus cereus*

Organism	Hours of incubation	OD values	Cyanide concentration (ppm/ml)	Degraded concentration of cyanide (ppm/ml)	Percentage of degradation	Biomass (mg/ml)
S3	24	0.354	510	430	45.74	8.23
	48	0.294	420	520	53.31	12.58
	72	0.206	290	650	69.14	26.39
	96	0.155	200	740	78.74	47.66

Table 4. Estimation of ammonia in enrichment media supplemented with 1% glucose for *Bacillus cereus*

Organism	OD values	Hours of incubation	Concentration of ammonia (µg/ml)	Biomass (mg/ml)
S3	0.427	72	44.94	26.39
	0.549	96	51.18	47.66

nide with the increase in dose of *Bacillus cereus* upto 2% and then it decreases. Increase in the biosorption with increasing dose of adsorbent is expected but in the present

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time.

study upto 2% inoculum cells containing cyanide hydratase were saturated with the cyanide binding sites. So a dose of 2% of *Bacillus cereus* was used for further study.

The effect of temperature was studied at 25 to 45 °C. Temperature plays a major role in the adsorption studies. Although, the magnitude of the heat effect for the biosorption process is one of the most important criteria for the efficient removal of heavy metals from the waste water. Temperature changes will affect a number of factors which are important in heavy metal ion biosorption³⁰. Some of the factors include (i) the stability of the metal ion species initially placed in solution; (ii) the stability of microorganism-metal complex depending on the biosorption sites; (iii) the effect of temperature on the microorganism cell wall configuration; (iv) the ionization of chemical moieties on the cell wall³¹. Studies on different incubation temperature revealed that the maximum biosorption of 84% was occurred at 35 °C after which the rate of reaction decreased sharply i.e. biosorption capacity of *Bacillus cereus* decreased rapidly (Table 6).

Fig. 8 represents the effect of initial pH of the solution on the biosorption of cyanide (940 ppm) onto *Bacillus cereus* (2%). The optimum pH was found to be pH 8 as it owing to be an alkali strain the maximum removal efficiency was 80% (Table 7). Consequently the working pH value for biosorption of cyanide onto *Bacillus cereus* was chosen as pH 8 and other adsorption experiments were performed at this pH value. Previous works have

Table 5. Effect of inoculum concentration on cyanide degradation by *Bacillus cereus*

Inoculum	Hrs	Cyanide concentration (ppm/ml)	Degraded cyanide (ppm/ml)	Percentage of degradation	Biomass (mg/ml)
1%	24	800	140	14.89	1.74
	48	620	320	34.04	5.89
	72	470	470	50.00	9.98
	96	310	630	67.02	18.90
2%	24	520	420	44.68	7.75
	48	325	615	65.42	11.34
	72	195	745	79.25	22.34
	96	110	830	88.29	24.88
3%	24	540	400	42.55	7.38
	48	360	580	61.70	10.69
	72	220	720	76.59	21.61
	96	130	810	86.17	24.29
4%	24	550	390	41.48	7.21
	48	400	540	57.44	9.95
	72	280	660	70.21	12.16
	96	195	745	79.25	13.75
5%	24	570	370	39.36	6.84
	48	440	500	53.19	9.21
	72	320	620	65.95	11.41
	96	235	705	75.00	21.16

Table 6. Effect of temperature on cyanide degradation by *Bacillus cereus*

Temp. (°C)	Hrs	Cyanide concentration (ppm/ml)	Degraded cyanide (ppm/ml)	Percentage of degradation	Biomass (mg/ml)
25	24	825	115	12.23	1.42
	48	650	290	30.85	5.33
	72	500	440	46.80	9.34
	96	365	575	61.17	17.25
30	24	800	140	14.89	1.74
	48	620	320	34.04	5.89
	72	470	470	50.00	9.98
	96	310	630	67.02	18.90
35	24	510	430	45.74	9.12
	48	390	550	58.51	11.67
	72	280	660	70.21	19.79
	96	150	790	84.04	23.68
40	24	890	50	5.61	0.081
	48	890	50	5.61	0.081
	72	890	50	5.61	0.081
	96	890	50	5.61	0.081
45	24	930	10	1.06	0.01
	48	930	10	1.06	0.01
	72	930	10	1.06	0.01
	96	930	10	1.06	0.01

Table 7. Effect of pH on cyanide degradation by *Bacillus cereus*

pH	Hrs	Cyanide concentration (ppm/ml)	Degraded cyanide (ppm/ml)	Percentage of degradation	Biomass (mg/ml)
5	24	900	40	4.25	0.08
	48	895	45	4.78	0.085
	72	895	45	4.78	0.085
	96	895	45	4.78	0.085
6	24	845	95	10.10	1.18
	48	820	120	12.76	1.49
	72	800	140	14.89	1.74
	96	790	150	15.95	1.86
7	24	800	140	14.89	1.74
	48	620	320	34.04	5.89
	72	470	470	50.00	9.98
	96	310	630	67.02	18.90
8	24	520	420	44.68	7.73
	48	410	530	56.38	10.75
	72	300	640	68.08	19.06
	96	180	760	80.85	22.63
9	24	760	180	19.14	2.23
	48	600	340	36.17	6.25
	72	450	490	52.12	10.41
	96	290	650	69.14	19.49

reported microbial degradation of cyanide at neutral or acidic conditions³²⁻³⁴. But the major challenge for biodegradation of cyanide compounds is the alkalinity of cyanide containing wastewaters and the volatilization of cyanide under neutral or acidic conditions to hydrocyanic acid (HCN), a weak acid with a pK_a value of 9.2. By contrast, references describing cyanide biodegradation at alkaline pH are scarce. *Marinobacter* species²⁷ are examples among those few which can produce novel enzymes capable of degrading cyanide at highly alkaline pH. Such microbes are the ones suitable for practical applications of cyanide biodegradation. Therefore, continuous search for cyanotrophic microorganisms capable of degrading cyanide at alkaline conditions is the principal element for the effort being made to develop efficient biotechnological methods of cyanide removal.

In addition, isolates were further characterized on the basis of their efficient utilization of different carbon sources. The effect of additional carbon sources on cyanide degradation is shown in Table 8. The incubation of bacterial strain *Bacillus cereus* in minimal medium having cyanide concentration of 940 ppm/ml (cyanide/mini-

mal medium) was performed with different concentrations of dextrose at temperature 35 °C, pH 8.0 for 72 h. It was observed that there was a maximum degradation (87.23%) of cyanide with the increasing concentration of glucose up to the level of 3%. Little fluctuation in the percent degradation with the increase in percentage above 3% after 48 h of incubation was noticed. But the percentage of degradation rate was higher at 4% and 5% during 24 and 48 h of incubation. This may be due to the fact that the increased glucose level may be extremely utilized by the *Bacillus cereus* for their rapid growth. However, presence of dextrose speeded up the cyanide degradation upto 3% very effectively. Ammonia was detected in all cases. The appearance of ammonia was possibly because of further hydrolysis of formamide by amidase enzyme to form formic acid and ammonia. Further, dehydrogenation reaction converted formic acid to carbon dioxide. It has been shown that growth of the strains was hardly recorded in glucose supplied media. One explanation for this could be a reaction between reducing sugars and cyanide, commonly taking place at highly alkaline pH and well documented as the Kiliani reaction^{35,36}. This reaction might

Table 8. Estimation of cyanide in enrichment media supplemented with different concentration of glucose for *Bacillus cereus*

Glucose concentration (%)	Hours of incubation	Cyanide concentration (ppm/ml)	Degraded concentration of cyanide (ppm/ml)	Percentage of cyanide	Biomass (mg/ml)
1	24	510	430	45.74	8.23
	48	420	520	53.31	12.58
	72	290	650	69.14	26.39
	96	200	740	78.74	47.66
2	24	430	510	54.25	12.80
	48	310	630	67.02	25.58
	72	205	735	78.19	47.32
	96	160	780	82.97	23.21
3	24	410	530	56.38	13.30
	48	280	660	70.21	42.50
	72	175	765	81.38	22.77
	96	120	820	87.23	24.40
4	24	400	540	57.44	13.55
	48	340	600	63.82	24.36
	72	320	620	65.96	25.17
	96	300	640	68.08	25.98
5	24	400	540	57.44	13.55
	48	350	590	62.76	23.94
	72	320	620	65.95	25.15
	96	300	640	68.08	25.98

have made nutrients unavailable and strains fail to utilize them. Dumestre *et al.*³⁷ also reported rapid loss of cyanide observed in glucose, galactose, lactose, and maltose minimal media even in uninoculated ones but not in saccharose minimal medium, yeast extract basal medium, or nutrient broth.

The sequences of the partial 16S rRNA of the potential isolate (1516 bp) was compared against those available in the public databases. They were closely related to those of *Bacillus cereus* (100% homology). The bacteria were thus identified as *B. cereus* (we designated the isolate as *Bacillus cereus* S3) and the nucleotide sequences of the potential cyanide degrading isolate from salt pan region have been deposited in the Gen-Bank database under accession number FJ267613. Only very few species of genus *Bacillus* and *Halomonas* having cyanide utilization properties are reported in the literature³⁸. This result can be a very good source to further study as to how the degradation process is taking place in bacteria other than the well characterized ones such as the *Pseudomonas* group.

The study of sorption kinetics is significant in biosorption process as it provides valuable insights into the reaction pathways and into the mechanism of sorption reactions. Therefore the present study was attempted to confirm with the following equations.

Bangham's equation : Bangham's equation³⁹ is given as :

$$\log \log (C_0 / (C_0 - qm_s)) = \log k_0 m_s / 2.303 + \alpha \log (t)$$

where V is the volume of solution, α (< 1) and k_0 are constants. The double logarithmic plot for S3 yields a linear curve for the degradation of cyanide ($R^2 = 0.942$) (Fig. 2). This shows that the film diffusion is the rate controlling parameter.

Intra-particle diffusion study : The most commonly used technique for identifying the mechanism involved in the degradation process is by using intra-particle diffusion model³⁸ as :

$$q = K_d t^{1/2} + I$$

where K_d is the intra-particle diffusion rate constant. If intra-particle diffusion occurs, then q against $t^{1/2}$ will be

Fig. 2. Bangham's plot.

linear and the line will pass through the origin if the intra-particle diffusion was the rate limiting parameter controlling the process. Otherwise, some other mechanism is also involved. Fig. 3 presents intra-particle plot. Values of I give an idea about the thickness of the boundary layer. The data indicate that intra-particle diffusion controls the sorption rate. Simultaneously, external mass transfer resistance cannot be neglected although this resistance is only significant for the initial period of time³⁹.

Fig. 3. Intra-particle plot.

Isotherm study : It is important to evaluate the most appropriate correlations for equilibrium curves, to optimize the design of a sorption system. Langmuir, Freundlich, Tempkin isotherm models were used to describe the adsorption equilibrium. Experimental isotherm data were conducted at an equilibrium time of 120 min for different dosages of adsorbate.

Tempkin isotherm, assumes that the heat of adsorption decreases linearly with the coverage due to adsorbent-adsorbate interaction. The adsorption is characterized by a uniform distribution of binding energies up to some maximum binding energy. The Tempkin isotherm has generally been applied in the following linear form :

$$q_e = B \ln K_T + B \ln C_e$$

where $B = RT/b$, K_T (L/g) is Tempkin isotherm constant, b (J/mol) is a constant related to heat of sorption, R is the gas constant (8.314 J/mol K) and T the absolute temperature (K). A plot of q_e versus $\ln C_e$ enables the determination of the isotherm constants B and K_T from the slope and intercept. K_T is the equilibrium binding constant (mol L⁻¹) corresponding to the maximum binding energy and constant B is related to the heat of adsorption. The plot (not shown) of $1/q_e$ vs $1/C_e$ does not yield straight line demonstrating that Langmuir isotherm not fits the sorption data very well ($r = 0.791$).

Tempkin isotherm contains a factor that explicitly takes into the account adsorbing species and adsorbent interactions. The heat of adsorption of all the molecules in the layer would decrease linearly with coverage due to adsorbate/adsorbant interaction^{40,41}. This isotherm assume that the heat of adsorption of all the molecules in the layer decreases linearly with coverage due to adsorbent and adsorbate interactions and that the adsorption is characterized by a uniform distribution of binding energy upto some maximum binding energy.

A plot of q_e vs $\ln C_e$ enables the determination of isotherm constants B and K_T from the slope and intercept respectively. Fig. 4 shows the Tempkin isotherm plot for the degradation of cyanide and the corresponding constants are presented in Table 9. A linear relationship between q_e and $\ln C_e$ indicates the applicability of this model to understand the degradation mechanism.

The correlation coefficient for the Tempkin isotherm is 0.989 which is higher in comparison to the values ob-

Table 9.

Freundlich constants	$\log k_f (\text{mg L}^{-1}) = 7.92$	$1/n = -1.51$	$R^2 = 0.8791$
Tempkins constants	$K_T (\text{mg L}^{-1}) = 71610$	$B = -10207$	$R^2 = 0.978$

Fig. 4. Tempkin plot.

tained for the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms. Therefore the Tempkin isotherm is the best fit isotherm for the degradation of cyanide onto *Bacillus cereus*.

The degradation kinetics was investigated using the pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order model. The kinetic studies show that the degradation process followed the pseudo-second order model.

Conversely, the kinetic data exhibited an excellent compliance with pseudo-second order kinetic equation. The plots of t/q_t against t at different strain showed excellent linearity (Fig. 5). The pseudo-second order rate constant k_2 , the calculated q_e values and corresponding linear regression correlation coefficients values R^2 are given in Table 10. As seen in Table 10, the calculated q_e values agree with experimental q_e values well and also, the correlation coefficients for the pseudo-second order kinetic plots at all the studied different organisms were significantly higher ($R^2 > 0.9$). The best correlation for the system provided by the pseudo-second order model suggested that cyanide concentration decreased with increasing the time.

The degradation kinetics is very important for the process design and operation control of a degradation pro-

Fig. 5. Pseudo-second order kinetic models for the degradation of cyanide using different isolates.

cess. The several kinetic approaches describing the transformation of organic compounds by suspended microorganisms have been evaluated using zero order, pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order rate kinetics. The experimental kinetic data were fitted by pseudo-second order models. The constants for all models were evaluated and listed in Table 10 and the corresponding plots are shown in Fig. 5.

One of the obstacles in using microorganism for bioremediation of cyanide containing waste is that most microorganisms capable of biodegrading cyanide are sensitive to cyanide concentration, with biodegradation and/or growth rate decreasing above specific thresholds for

Table 10. Pseudo-second order kinetic models for the degradation of cyanide using different isolates

Kinetic models	Different organism	Kinetic parameters		
		q_e cal (mg/g)	k_1	R^2
Second-order kinetics	S1	0.564	0.1608	0.956
	S2	0.378	1.2594	0.993
	S3	0.808	0.0915	0.997
	S4	0.442	0.3450	0.994
	S3 + 1% Glucose	1.993	0.0224	0.960

each organism. *Bacillus cereus* obtained from salt pan used under present study, on the other hand was found to be growing up to 940 ppm/ml (cyanide concentration/minimal medium) after acclimatization. Possibly its ability of cyanide tolerance can be further increased. Biological treatment processes has a much lower operating cost when compared to chemical treatment processes and it allows both the removal of cyanide and denitrification of the ammonia produced as a result of the cyanide removal. This in turn results in a much more environmentally friendly effluent. Biological treatment is an ecosociable approach for removal of cyanide from industrial waste as well as from polluted natural bodies. It can be less expensive and much faster than chemical and physical methods (Dwivadi 2011). So, it can be concluded from the present investigation that the native isolate haloalkaliphilic *Bacillus cereus* isolate from Tuticorin region, possess more potential in degrading cyanide than the isolates in effluent streams.

Conclusion

The results of present study undoubtedly reveal that *Bacillus cereus* has strong potentialities to degrade cyanide and hence can be employed as a bio-agent for cyanide detoxification from the contaminated effluents. Physical and chemical treatments which are being utilized for the removal of cyanide are expensive and difficult to operate while biological treatments are less expensive, much faster and eco-friendly than chemical and physical methods. Biological treatment of cyanide waste may lead to generate less toxic amide and fewer amounts of acidic products, carbon-dioxide and mainly ammonia. It can be concluded that alkaliphilic bacterial strains screened in this study evidentially show the potential to possess degradative activities that can be harnessed to remediate cyanide wastes.

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